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The Multipoint Axial Thermometry Protocol of Death-time Estimation

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Abstract—The postmortem axial thermal profile of a body was recently demonstrated to have high specificity for the number of minutes elapsed after death, in comparison to a body's single-point core (rectal) thermometry temperature value applied by today's methods of death-time estimation. Application of multipoint axial thermometry (MAT) was recently proposed for death-time estimation to eliminate uncertainties of single-point thermometry that include the postmortem temperature plateau phenomenon and non-standardisation of thermometry-depth and body radius. Subsequently, a MAT device prototype was proposed and its application demonstrated both empirically and numerically. This paper proposes the MAT Protocol of Death-time Estimation: a MAT profile is first measured from a body found dead using the proposed MAT device. The MAT profile is systemically compared against MAT profiles produced by multiple numerical simulations of incrementally increased postmortem intervals (PMIs). The numerical simulations apply a 3D computational human model of comparable age, sex and anthropometry to the dead body, and also apply a virtual MAT device identical to the physical MAT device. The spatial orientation of the virtual MAT device inside the 3D computational human model and the anatomical region in which it is inserted are identical to those in the dead body. The numerical simulations apply exact ambient temperatures that existed during a simulated PMI from a source of historical meteorological data. A PMI simulation that produces a matching MAT profile is regarded as the final PMI estimated by the Protocol. Principles of application of the Protocol in forensic pathology are demonstrated in this paper.

Keywords — multipoint axial thermometry, MAT Protocol, single-point thermometry, postmortem interval, death-time estimation.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE postmortem axial thermal profile of a body has been demonstrated to be highly specific to the length of time elapsed after death [1] in comparison to single-point core thermometry temperature that today's death-time estimation methods apply, typically rectal temperature applied in the rectal temperature nomogram method [2] [3]. Single-point thermometry detects the temperature of a central isotherm that exists at whatever body-depth is reached by the tip of the thermometer being used. Central isotherms can persist for several hours inside the body as their radii gradually reduce. Single-point thermometry of a central isotherm manifests as the problematic postmortem temperature plateau (PMTP) phenomenon. The PMTP length measured from a body found dead was shown to depend on several factors, including the interval between death and thermometry (i.e., the postmortem interval, or PMI, of that body), the ratio of the radius of the antemortem central isotherm at death to body-radius at the thermometry site, thermometry-depth and body radius [1]. These four factors are not standardised before death-time estimation by modern-day methods, and each thus constitutes a source of uncertainty.

The application of multipoint axial thermometry (MAT) – the measurement of a body's postmortem axial thermal profile – was suggested for death-time estimation to

eliminate the aforementioned sources of uncertainty associated with single-point thermometry. MAT was later demonstrated empirically and numerically [4]. The postmortem MAT profile curve from the body centre was shown to be a parabola having the highest temperature in the body core and the lowest temperature on the skin. This paper proposes a method of death-time estimation that applies the postmortem MAT profile of a body.

II. METHOD

The proposed MAT Protocol of Death-time Estimation is a method by which the length of time from death to MAT (the PMI of a body found dead that is to be estimated) necessary to produce a MAT profile measured from the body using a MAT device proposed by Mfolozi [4], is determined. The Protocol (Fig. 1) systemically compares the measured MAT profile against MAT profiles numerically produced by simulations of increasingly longer test-PMIs, beginning with the zero-minute test-PMI. Each test-PMI has a corresponding 'time of death' that is back-calculated from the time of MAT. The body's antemortem temperature distribution that would have existed at a 'time of death' in question is numerically approximated using methods described by Mfolozi [5].

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Postmortem cooling that would have occurred between the ‘time of death’ and time of MAT is numerically simulated using methods described by Mfolozi [1]. Thereafter, MAT is numerically performed using methods previously described [4]. The two MAT profiles are then compared. A match means that the simulated PMI is the PMI required to produce the MAT profile measured from the body, which is then regarded as the final PMI estimated by the Protocol. If the MAT profiles do not match, the Protocol is repeated for a slightly longer test-PMI until a match is found. The Protocol consists of 9 sequential steps, the first four of which are performed only once and the rest repeated as required.

Fig. 1. A schematic depiction of the MAT Protocol of Death-time Estimation.

Step 1. Examine the body

Examination of the dead body is required before the MAT Protocol is applied. Bodyweight, height, age, sex, position (prone, supine, lateral, foetal), posture (joint angles), clothing/coverings and ground-surface must be established. Body circumference where MAT is to be undertaken must also be measured. This information is used later to select a comparable 3D computational human model with which the Protocol is applied.

Step 2. Perform multipoint axial thermometry

The choice of a body part where MAT is undertaken is informed by several factors, including the examiner’s personal preference, need for preservation of important antemortem pathology relevant to the cause of death, avoidance of creating postmortem artefacts that may later confound autopsy findings, etc. The body site proposed by

this paper for MAT is the thigh – it is roughly circular, has a relatively large radius compared to the body trunk, and contains mostly skeletal muscle not routinely dissected at autopsy. It is suggested that the MAT device is inserted to pass through the centre of the thigh. The 3-axis orientation of the MAT device relative to the body part is recorded for later application during the comparison stage. The circumference of the body part where the device is inserted (thigh) is measured. The time of insertion of the MAT device into the body and the time when the MAT profile is actually measured are recorded, the difference of which constitutes the thermal equilibration period.

Step 3. Investigate the death scene

The air temperature existing at the time of MAT is measured. The type of surface on which the body is found is noted so that its material properties can be established. Environmental factors that influence the rate of postmortem cooling, such as nearby sources of thermal radiation or heat sinks, are noted. Where possible, the sort of antemortem physical activity undertaken by the decedent at the moment of death is approximated using findings from the death scene.

Step 4. Collect historical meteorological data

The location of the body is ascertained, preferably using a global position system (GPS) enabled device if the death scene is outdoors. Historical meteorological data (air temperature) of the GPS coordinates are obtained from the nearest weather station. For indoor death scenes, the air temperature measured in Step 3 is assumed to have existed at the time of death and during postmortem cooling.

Step 5. Computationally model the body and death scene

Data collected in Step 1 are used to select a comparable 3D computational human model from a library [6]. The topography and temperature of the ground surface noted in Step 3 are numerically modelled in the thermal solver. Material properties (density, specific heat capacity and thermal conductivity) of the ground surface identified in Step 3 are obtained from the literature. The selected 3D computational human model is placed on the ground surface to assume the body position as recorded in Step 1. Major joints of the 3D computational human model are manipulated to pose the model in the posture of the body.

Step 6. Approximate the antemortem body temperature

The antemortem body temperature is numerically approximated on the 3D computational human model selected in Step 5 using methods previously mentioned [5]. The initial condition of the 3D computational human model can be any arbitrary temperature value. The boundary condition is the air temperature that existed at the operative 'time of death' being tested, the value of which is obtained from Step 4 data. The initial condition of the ground surface is the same as the boundary condition. The boundary condition type is 'mixed'. The heat transfer coefficient (h) value applied is that appropriate for body position and existing heat transfer conditions [7]. The metabolic equivalent value of the antemortem activity approximated in Step 3 is obtained from the literature [8] and systematically distributed to thermogenic organs of the 3D computational human model to determine appropriate tissue metabolic-heat-generation (Q_m) and blood perfusion (ω_b) parameters. Standard tissue parameters for density (ρ), specific heat capacity (C) and thermal conductivity (k) are obtained from the literature [9]. The simulation length is that appropriate to produce a stable solution. The simulation that approximates antemortem body temperature distribution is referred to as the AM (antemortem) simulation in the Protocol.

Step 7. Simulate postmortem cooling

The solution of the Step 6 simulation forms the initial condition for numerical simulation of postmortem cooling using methods previously described [1]. The length of the numerical simulation of postmortem cooling depends on the length of the test-PMI, as well as on the periodicity at which historical meteorological data were recorded by the weather station. Most meteorological data are recorded once every hour. The boundary condition is the air temperature that existed during the test-PMI. If more than one air temperature value (boundary condition) appears in the meteorological record during the test-PMI, the numerical simulation is divided into separate, shorter simulations in which each air temperature value constitutes a boundary condition. In such a split, the solution of the preceding numerical simulation forms initial conditions for the succeeding simulation. The boundary condition in all simulations is the 'mixed' type. The boundary condition value applied is that appropriate for the specific postmortem cooling condition concerned. Simulation of postmortem cooling terminates at the time of insertion of the MAT into the body as recorded in Step 2. Numerical simulations of postmortem cooling are referred to as PM (postmortem) simulations in the Protocol, of

which may be several and would therefore be denoted by a number, e.g., PM-1, PM-2, etc.

Step 8. Simulate the MAT procedure

The solution of the Step 7 simulation forms the initial condition of the MAT simulation, in which a virtual MAT device identical to the physical MAT device used in Step 2 is computationally inserted into the 3D computational human model's corresponding body as undertaken in Step 2. The 3-axis orientation of the inserted virtual MAT device is manipulated to be identical to that recorded in Step 2. The length of the MAT simulation is adjusted to be equal to the thermal equilibration time recorded in Step 2. The boundary condition is the death scene air temperature measured in Step 3. The boundary condition type 'mixed'. The heat transfer coefficient is that appropriate for the time MAT was undertaken.

Step 9. Compare MAT profiles

The solution of the Step 8 simulation is analysed, and temperatures of virtual MAT sensors constitute the simulated MAT profile, which is plotted on a graph along with the MAT profile obtained from Step 2. Both will have parabolic shapes. If the two curves match, the test-PMI is regarded as the PMI required to produce the MAT profile measured in Step 2, which is then regarded as the final PMI estimated by the Protocol. When the curves don't match, a slightly longer test-PMI is selected and the Protocol repeated from Step 6 to Step 9. Since the Protocol begins by testing the zero-minute test-PMI, a sufficiently long test-PMI that produces a matching MAT profile will inevitably be found, as long as the body temperature has not equilibrated with ambient temperature. After body temperature has equilibrated with ambient temperature, the Protocol informs of the minimum PMI required for such thermal equilibration.

III. DEMONSTRATION

The principle of application of the MAT Protocol is demonstrated in this paper using a fictitious scenario in which Steps 1, 2 and 3 are assumed to have already been performed. Legal and logistical constraints prevented the demonstration of the Protocol using a recently deceased human body, which would have been ideal.

A. The given (fictitious) scenario requiring death-time estimation using the MAT Protocol

On the morning of Saturday April 22nd 2018, the naked body of a 70.2kg, 1.77m tall male was found hanging by the neck from a tree in a wooded area. The body bore marks of non-fatal torture. The GPS coordinates of the body were 40°46'40" N, 73°58'11" W. The MAT device was inserted at 11H25 local-time through the proximal aspect of the right thigh in the parasagittal plane where the thigh circumference was 50cm. Thermal equilibration took 8 minutes (500s) and the final MAT profile was obtained at 11H33. Fig. 2 indicates the curve plotted from the MAT profile temperatures. A corresponding excel spreadsheet with temperatures values and respective sensor numbers was provided. The ambient air temperature measured next to the body at 11H33 was 15.1°C. The task is to apply the MAT Protocol to estimate the PMI and/or time of death using the information provided.

Fig. 2. A plotted curve of the MAT profile measured from the thigh, whose unknown PMI and must be estimated using the MAT Protocol.

B. Historical meteorological data

The first step was to acquire historical meteorological data from the nearest weather station using the information provided. The use of the Google Earth application established that the provided GPS coordinates were of a wooded location in Central Park of New York City in the USA. A historical meteorological record of that location for April 22nd, 2018, was obtained from www.wunderground.com [10]. The record indicated that air temperature measurements in the preceding hours had been made 51 minutes into every hour as indicated in Table 1.

The 1-hour periodic nature of this meteorological record meant that air temperatures had not been recorded during 59 of the 60 minutes in an hour, whereas the nature of the MAT Protocol required air temperatures during the entire

Time	Measured air temperature
11H51	16.7°C
10H51	13.9°C
09H51	12.2°C
08H51	10.6°C
07H51	8.9°C
06H51	7.8°C
05H51	6.7°C
04H51	7.9°C
03H51	8.3°C
02H51	8.9°C
01H51	10.0°C
00H51	11.1°C

Table 1. Historical meteorological record from a weather station nearest to the supplied GPS coordinates for the 12 hours preceding MAT.

record to be known. To overcome this, the rate of temperature change per minute was first calculated for each hour interval using the formula:

$$R = \frac{T_y - T_x}{60 \text{ mins}}, \quad t = y - x \quad (1)$$

where R is the per-minute rate of temperature change between times x and y , T_x is air temperature recorded at time x , T_y is air temperature recorded at time y , and time x existed before time y . Per-minute rates so calculated are indicated in Table 2.

Time interval (time x) - (time y)	Per Minute Temperature Change Rate (°C/min)
00H51 - 01H51	-0.0183
01H51 - 02H51	-0.0183
02H51 - 03H51	-0.01
03H51 - 04H51	-0.007
04H51 - 05H51	-0.02
05H51 - 06H51	+0.0183
06H51 - 07H51	+0.0183
07H51 - 08H51	+0.0283
08H51 - 09H51	+0.0267
09H51 - 10H51	+0.0283
10H51 - 11H33	+0.0286

Table 2. Per-minute rates of temperature change of the meteorological record calculated using eqn. 1.

Air temperatures at any arbitrary time within any 1-hour interval in Table 2 were then interpolated using the formula:

$$T_w = T_x + Rt_w, \quad t_w = w - x \quad (2)$$

where T_w is air temperature at any arbitrary time w , T_x is air temperature at time x existing in the relevant 1-hour interval, R is the per-minute rate of temperature change in the relevant 1-hour interval, t_w is the number of minutes between time x and time w , and time x existed before time w . Air temperatures interpolated using eqn. (2) were to be applied in boundary conditions of all AM and PM simulations.

C. Computational modelling of the body & death scene

The 3D computational human model selected for the Protocol was Duke, who was built from magnetic resonance images of a 34-year-old, 1.77m tall male with a mass of 70.2kg [6]. No ground surface was modelled because the body was found hanging by the neck. The 3D computational human model was not posed.

D. The zero-minute Test-PMI

The operative ‘time of death’ of this test-PMI was 11H33, the time of MAT by the device. In this test-PMI, the MAT device would have been inserted 500s before death, therefore no postmortem cooling would have occurred. The measured MAT profile would therefore be that which would have existed in life. An AM simulation to approximate the antemortem temperature distribution was performed as described previously. The initial condition was arbitrarily set to 37°C. The boundary condition was 15.1°C, which was the air temperature measured at the vicinity of the body. The value applied to the boundary condition was 9.5 W/m²/K for a vertical cylinder cooling in natural convective conditions [11]. The boundary condition type was ‘mixed’. The simulation interval was 9000s [5]. Average tissue parameters Q_m , ω_b , ρ , C and k were applied [9].

On completion of the AM simulation, a 500s-long AM simulation representing thermal equilibration of the MAT device in the body was performed, which would have occurred antemortem in this test-PMI. A boundary condition of 14.988°C was applied, calculated using eqn. (2). The boundary condition type and value applied were unchanged. Organ parameters applied were also unchanged. The virtual MAT device was computationally inserted where the 3D computational human model’s right thigh had a circumference of 50cm. The MAT profile from this simulation was derived and plotted with the MAT profile obtained from the body. Fig. 3 indicates the two MAT curves plotted on the same graph. The two MAT profile curves clearly do not match. Therefore, a 0-hour test-PMI could not have produced the MAT profile curve

Fig. 3. The unknown-PMI MAT profile curve (red) plotted with the zero-minute test-PMI MAT profile curve (green).

provided. Therefore, the Protocol was repeated, but for the 1-hour test-PMI.

E. Test-PMIs > zero-minutes

The test-PMIs 1hr, 2hrs, 3hrs, 4hrs and 5hrs were sequentially tested using MAT Protocol Steps 6 to 9 as described earlier. Simulated MAT profile curves for test-PMIs 1hr, 2hrs, 3hrs and 4hrs indicated higher temperatures compared to the MAT profile curve provided, while the simulated MAT profile curve for the 5hrs test-PMI indicated lower temperatures. This was interpreted to mean that the unknown PMI was longer than 4hrs but shorter than 5hrs.

Therefore, the MAT Protocol was refined and the test-PMIs 4hrs10min, 4hrs20min, 4hrs30min, 4hrs40min and 4hrs50min were sequentially tested in a manner described in the previous sections. Simulated MAT profile curves for test-PMIs 4hrs10min, 4hrs20min, 4hrs30min and 4hrs40min indicated higher temperatures compared to the MAT profile curve provided, while the simulated MAT profile curve for the 4hrs50min test-PMI indicated lower temperatures. This was interpreted to mean that the unknown PMI was longer than 4hrs40min but shorter than 4hrs50min.

Once more, the MAT Protocol was refined and the test-PMIs 4hrs42min, 4hrs44min, 4hrs46min and 4hrs48min were sequentially tested in a manner described in the previous sections. The simulated MAT profile curve for the 4hrs42min test-PMI indicated higher temperatures compared to the provided MAT profile curve, while the simulated MAT profile curve for the 4hrs44min test-PMI matched the provided MAT profile exactly, wherein all corresponding curve temperature values matched to the fifth decimal, i.e., their difference was 0.00000°C. For the scenario provided, 4hrs44min was thus regarded as the

PMI required to produce the MAT profile curve measured from the body, all else considered. Therefore, the back-calculated time of death estimation by the Protocol was 06H49 on April 22nd, 2018. The Protocol was therefore terminated at this point without testing the remaining test-PMIs. Fig. 4 indicates the two overlapping MAT profile curves plotted on the same graph. A summary of the MAT Protocol that produced a MAT match is indicated in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4. Indicates the unknown-PMI MAT profile curve overlapped by the 4hr44min MAT profile curve.

IV. DISCUSSION

1. Application of meteorological air temperature values

All methods of death-time estimation require the application of the air temperature value that existed during postmortem cooling, as it determines the rate of postmortem cooling. Death-time estimation methods based on Marshal and Hoare's Cooling Formula [12], such as the Rectal Temperature Nomogram method [2] [3], advise the application of an averaged air temperature value from historical meteorological data of the weather station nearest to the body. However, to average air temperature values, the time when death occurred needs to first be known so that air temperature values that existed between that time and time of thermometry (this interval is the PMI to be estimated) are those that are averaged. The fact that the time of death is the unknown being solved for therefore constitutes a source of uncertainty of death-time estimations by methods that apply the averaged air temperature procedure. By contrast, the boundary conditions applied in the Protocol in this demonstration, which confirmed the 4hr44min test-PMI, were air temperature values that exclusively existed exactly during the 4hr44min postmortem cooling interval. Therefore, the

Simulation Details	AM	PM 1	PM 2	PM 3	PM 4	PM 5	Isotherm measurement
Simulation interval	9000s	3600s	3600s	3600s	3600s	2100s	500s
Simulated period	Alive-06H49	06H49-07H49	07H49-08H49	08H49-09H49	09H49-10H49	10H49-11H25	11H25-11H33
Initial condition	37°C	AM	PM 1	PM 2	PM 3	PM 4	PM 5 for 3D human
Boundary condition	7.761°C	8.311°C	9.701°C	11.345°C	12.995°C	14.358°C	15.1°C for virtual sensor
Boundary type	mixed	mixed	mixed	mixed	mixed	mixed	14.988°C
Heat transfer coefficient [W/(m²K)]	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5
Grid cells (x10 ⁷)	3.4595	3.4595	3.4595	3.4595	3.4595	3.4595	9.1563
Time to solution	28hrs	10hr4min	10hr36min	10hr4min	10hr36min	6hrs	5hrs34min

Fig. 5. Summary of the MAT Protocol that confirmed the 4hrs44min test-PMI.

Protocol did away with averaging air temperature values, thus eliminating the associated uncertainty.

2. Approximation of antemortem body temperature

Death-time estimation methods based on the Cooling Formula, such as the Rectal temperature Nomogram method, apply a single-point approximation of the antemortem body temperature in the form of a 37°C value, as stated before. These methods do not approximate the antemortem temperature distribution of the whole body and do not quantify the ratio of antemortem central isotherm (ACI) radius to body-radius (r_{ACI}/r_{body}) present

at the thermometry site at the moment of death, which is now known to be one of several predictors of PMTP length [1]. On the other hand, the AM simulation always performed at the beginning of a MAT Protocol automatically approximates this ratio, specifically for a given boundary condition (air temperature) that existed at the operative ‘time of death’ of the test-PMI. The Protocol does not assume that the human body has the same antemortem temperature distribution at death irrespective of the prevailing boundary condition.

3. Protocol layout

The Protocol demonstrated in this paper was commenced from the zero-minute test-PMI. The Protocol may, however, be commenced at any test-PMI. Commencing at the zero-minute test-PMI was a systematic way to include all possible PMIs and illustrate the trend created by adding 1-hour increments during MAT profile comparison. In addition, the initially applied 1-hour increment was also chosen arbitrarily: any increment length may be chosen depending on the differences demonstrated during MAT profile comparison. Progressively shorter increments were applied in later iteration cycles of the Protocol in this demonstration.

The number of PM simulations undertaken in this demonstration increased as test-PMIs became longer. As PM simulations that follow after an AM simulation stack up, each applies a different boundary condition depending on variability of meteorological air temperature. Fig. 6 indicates the layout of AM and PM simulations in iterative applications of the Protocol to test progressively longer test-PMIs. The sequence in which boundary conditions are applied in AM and PM simulations is unique for each test-PMI.

Fig. 6. Layout of AM and PM simulations in iterative applications of the Protocol during a typical death-time estimation operation. The colour indicates air temperature applied in the boundary condition. Arrows indicate application of preceding simulation solutions as initial conditions for succeeding simulations. The iteration direction is from left to right.

4. Computational time

The demonstration presented in this paper consisted of 14 iteration cycles of the Protocol, which excluded 13 test-PMIs. The combined computational time of all the Protocol iterations for this demonstration was 3 months, which mostly consisted of the computer running simulations 24 hours-a-day and 7 days-a-week. The Protocol that tested the 4hrs44mins test-PMI alone took 71 hours to complete, as indicated in Fig. 5. Computational times exclude times taken to set up simulations and to input the required simulation data. The long computational times of executing the Protocol were the result of only one thermal solver license being available for the one computer used. This meant that only one simulation could be performed at a time, while others waited in the queue. The MAT Protocol can, however, be implemented simultaneously on multiple computer platforms, licensing regulations permitting, wherein a simulation sequence that tests one test-PMI is undertaken by one dedicated computer. A MAT profile match by one platform would therefore negate further tests in the other platforms. In such a scenario, the plurality of computer platforms would have to be synchronized and centralized in a server of sorts. Abundant computational resources, such as the use of a cluster computer, would therefore shorten the computational time significantly to make the Protocol practical for forensic application.

5. Independence from PMTP uncertainty

The 3D computational human model used in this demonstration has a known PMTP of 3hr51min [1] under specific simulation conditions. Despite this, the MAT Protocol demonstrated in this study was able to eliminate test-PMIs that were within this PMTP period, something single-point thermometry methods of death-time estimation are not capable of, by definition. The Protocol was able to do this because it compared MAT profiles that existed during the PMTP period, instead of accepting that the body core temperature remained unchanged, as would single-point thermometry perceive. Death-time estimation by the Protocol was not based on Marshal and Hoare’s Cooling Formula [12] and therefore did not require prior solving of Cooling Formula constants that include the body’s PMPT, as discussed previously [1]. The Protocol is therefore regarded as being free of the PMTP uncertainty.

6. Independence from thermometry-depth uncertainty

The proposed Protocol is free of the thermometry-depth uncertainty because a MAT profile naturally consists of multiple temperature values simultaneously measured at known body depths, which are compared to simulated

MAT profiles obtained from identical thermometry-depths of a comparable 3D computational human model.

7. Independence from body radius uncertainty

Body radius is an independent variable known to predict PMTP length, and hence the value of postmortem core temperature measured by single-point thermometry [13]. Body parts that have smaller radii have shorter PMTPs and cool faster. Non-standardization of body radius at the thermometry site by death-time estimation methods that apply single-point thermometry constitutes a source of uncertainty. The proposed MAT Protocol measures body circumference where MAT is undertaken and obtains the tested virtual MAT profile from the 3D computational human model's body part of identical circumference, thereby eliminating the body radius uncertainty.

8. Validation

Numerical methods of death-time estimation, such as the heat flow Finite Element Model [14] [15], are often validated against single-point death-time estimation methods such as the Rectal Temperature Nomogram method [2] [3]. The risk of such a validation approach is that the uncertainties associated with single-point thermometry discussed in this paper are potentially inherited by those numerical methods. However, the PMI estimation by the Protocol in this demonstration could not be validated against the Rectal Temperature Nomogram method because the Protocol applied a MAT profile consisting of multiple temperature measurements taken simultaneously at multiple thermometry depths. To make such validation, the PMI estimated by the Protocol would need to be compared against a PMI estimated using a temperature measurement from one of the 62 MAT device's temperature sensors, each of which corresponds to a different thermometry-depth. Each sensor recorded a slightly different temperature; therefore, each single-point temperature measurement would have yielded a slightly different death-time estimate on the nomogram. The choice of one thermometry-depth (temperature sensor) temperature value over another would be difficult to justify given the now-known nature of postmortem axial heat transfer as previously demonstrated [1].

9. PMI independence

The PMI of a body found dead is a natural method that reduces its r_{ACI}/r_{body} ratio by the time thermometry is undertaken for death-time estimation [1]. The PMI of a body is therefore itself another factor that predicts the (remaining) PMTP length of that body, which is measured for the first time at thermometry and therefore regarded as

being *the* body's PMTP. This fact means that priori knowledge of a body's PMI is a requirement in the application of the Cooling Formula and any other death-time estimation method based on it. This requirement, similar to that for averaging historical meteorological temperature values discussed earlier, is problematic because it is counterintuitive and, thus, represents a source of uncertainty. As stated earlier, the MAT Protocol is not based on the Cooling Formula and therefore does not require priori knowledge of the PMI to solve for variables that are then applied back into the calculation for PMI estimation. The MAT Protocol can test any and all possible test-PMIs individually.

10. New sources of uncertainty

While the aim of the proposed Protocol was to eliminate uncertainties associated with single-point thermometry and the PMTP after they were understood, the Protocol invariably applies a number of assumptions and methods that constitute a new set of uncertainties unique to it. Some of these include:

- 10.1 Anatomical and anthropometric representativity of the chosen 3D computational human model to the dead body.
- 10.2 The unknown antemortem physical activity state of the dead body,
- 10.3 Numerical simulation techniques and methods,
- 10.4 Accuracy of the approximated antemortem temperature distribution of the 3D human phantom in relation to that which existed in the body at death.
- 10.5 Accuracy of the boundary condition and temperature value in representing true conditions that existed during postmortem cooling.
- 10.6 Accuracy of the applied tissue parameters in both AM and PM simulations in representing those of the body found dead [16].
- 10.7 Accuracy of the applied ground-surface material properties in representing those at the death scene.
- 10.8 MAT device calibration and instrument error.
- 10.9 Accuracy of the virtual MAT device design and material properties in representing those of the physical device.
- 10.10 Accuracy of the 3-axis orientation of the virtual MAT device in the 3D human phantom in representing that of the physical MAT device in the dead body.
- 10.11 General human error during data handling and manual simulation setups.
- 10.12 Grid size and grid refinement.

An in-depth discussion of how these may constitute sources of uncertainty for the proposed Protocol is beyond the scope of this paper and is the subject of future research.

V. CONCLUSION

The MAT Protocol of Death-time Estimation proposed in this paper is an initial step in the elimination of uncertainties that arise from the application of single-point thermometry in death-time estimation. The conceptual demonstration promises that the Protocol could work in casework as envisaged. More work is required in its further development, particularly in the description, quantification and reduction of sources of uncertainty that will characterise it.

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